

Seed priming improves crop establishment of rice in flooded soils

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Direct seeding has become more popular among rice farmers because it requires less labor and time than transplanting, is cheaper, and can result in earlier harvest (Tuong et al 2000, Pandey and Velasco 2002). However, poor germination and uneven stand establishment caused by waterlogging or early floods, as well as high weed infestation, are among the main constraints to its large-scale adoption. This is because of the high sensitivity of rice to both flooding during germination and weed infestation during early seedling establishment (Pandey and Velasco 2002, Ismail et al 2009). Early flooding helps control most of the weeds commonly associated with rice. The use of genotypes tolerant of flooding during germination, together with proper management of seeds and the seedbed at sowing, can enhance crop establishment and ensure wider adoption of direct seeding (Ella et al 2010). Rice seed can germinate under flooded conditions, but subsequent growth is mostly limited to coleoptile growth and only tolerant genotypes have the ability to elongate and produce healthy seedlings (Ismail et al 2009).

Knowledge of the practices that prolong seed longevity through proper storage and handling, as well as optimum seedbed conditions and proper seed conditioning before sowing, can facilitate the development of management options that further augment and stabilize the performance of tolerant cultivars to ensure good crop establishment in flooded soils. This study evaluated the effects of seed priming (soaking followed by drying and storage for 1 to 2 months before sowing) on rice crop establishment in flooded soil. Seeds of four genotypes varying in tolerance of flooding during germination and early seedling stage were used in Experiment I while eight genotypes were used in Experiment II. Seeds were primed with water or with KCl for 24 h and 48 h in Experiment I while priming in Experiment II was done only in one duration (48 h), using two salt solutions (KCl and CaCl₂) of three concentrations each, varying

in osmotic potentials, and then sown dry in soil and flooded with 10 cm of tap water. Seedlings that reached above the water surface were counted as surviving at 21 d after sowing. In addition to survival, total amylase activity 3 d after flooding was also measured in Experiment II.

Priming improved seedling survival and establishment. The increase in survival was higher in the flooded setup than in control seedlings (Fig. 1A). Priming for 24 h significantly improved survival under flooded conditions (Fig. 1B), with higher survival in the tolerant genotypes than in the intolerant genotypes. However, priming with water had a negative effect when the priming duration was prolonged to 48 h, even in normally watered seedlings (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Seedling survival under (A) control and (B) flooded conditions of four rice genotypes as affected by priming using water (0 M) and 0.45 M KCl solution before sowing. Data are from Experiment I. Vertical bars indicate LSD at $P < 0.05$.

The viability of embryos of the growing seedlings was tested by staining a few longitudinal sections of 2-d-old seedlings with 2, 3, 5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride solution, which is colorless but turns into a deep red insoluble triphenylformazan after hydrogenation with the embryonic tissue of viable seed (Cottrell 1947). The growing embryo showed signs of damage in seeds primed with water for 48 h, as indicated by the faint staining 2 d after sowing. However, survival improved further when priming with KCl solution was prolonged for 48 h, probably due to the slow imbibition during priming of seeds with salt solution whose osmotic potential is less than in water. The negative effect of prolonged priming with tap water for 48 h could be attributed to faster imbibition in which seeds might have passed the activation stage of germination and entered the growing state, when the embryo became sensitive to dehydration during drying of seeds for storage before sowing.

The same trend was observed in Experiment II, in which survival in both control (not flooded) and flooded seedlings increased with priming. Higher survival occurred in seeds primed with KCl solution than with CaCl₂, also in salt solution with osmotic potential of -1.5 and -2.25 instead of -0.75 MPa, and in Khaiyan and Khao Hlan On more than in the other genotypes used (Fig. 2). The positive effect of priming on survival was less in the control treatment (Fig. 2A) than in the flooded seedlings (Fig. 2B) because of the high rate of germination under the controlled conditions, as observed in the first experiment. There were no significant interactive effects among the three variables: kind of salt, osmotic potential of the priming solution, and genotype. Shoot elongation was faster in seedlings from primed seeds, and this is more evident in the tolerant genotypes. Seedlings of tolerant genotypes derived from primed seeds reached the soil surface earlier (5 to 6 d after sowing and flooding) than those from the control seeds (about 8 to 9 d), and a more uniform growth was observed in primed seeds. This is consistent with the trend in total amylase activity, the major enzymes involved in starch breakdown for use by the growing embryos. Seedlings germinating from primed seeds had greater total amylase activity than those from unprimed seeds, and the activity was higher in tolerant genotypes (Fig. 3). Total amylase activity correlated positively with survival ($r = 0.73$, $n = 48$).

Fig. 3. Effect of seed priming for 48 h with KCl solutions of different concentrations on total amylase activity 3 d after sowing and flooding in soil. Vertical bar indicates LSD at $P<0.05$.

Our data indicate that seed priming helps improve seedling establishment in flooded soil, especially when seeds of tolerant genotypes were used, and this will be effective in rainfed areas where primed seeds can be stored until sufficient rainwater accumulates in the field. Priming enhanced germination and seedling growth in flooded soils, and improved the breakdown of stored carbohydrates by increasing the activity of amylase enzymes. Priming can be achieved using tap water for 24 h or salt solution such as KCl for prolonged priming of up to 48 h.

References

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